

Comparative studies on the efficiency of filters of different brands of cigarettes in reducing nicotine and other hazardous chemicals from smoke condensates – A gas chromatography-mass spectrometry study

Ashutosh Chakraborty^a and Sujit Chandra Lahiri*

Central Forensic Science Laboratory, 30, Gorachand Road, Kolkata-700 014, India

E-mail : sujitclahiri@yahoo.com, c.ashu@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received online 02 October 2012, accepted 06 November 2012

Abstract : Smoking of cigarettes, a tobacco product has been found to be hazardous to the consumers due to the presence of addictive and toxic chemical nicotine and a large number of hazardous chemicals like carbonmonoxide, hydrocyanic acid, polyaromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) etc. in cigarette smoke condensates. The compounds are responsible for heart diseases and cancers. However, manufacture of cigarettes is associated with employment, tax generation and profit. Attempts have been made to produce filter tipped cigarettes with suitable adsorbents of hazardous chemicals to make cigarette smoking pleasant and less injurious to health.

Comparative studies on the constituents of filters of different makes and their effectiveness in reducing injurious constituents of smoke condensates of different cigarettes had been made. Chloroform is used as solvent and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was used for the identification of the chemical constituents of filters and absorbed chemicals from smoke condensates. Triacetin with citroflex based and triacetin with dipropylene (diethylene) glycobenzoate were found to be most effective to arrest the most hazardous compound nicotine and other chemicals. Adsorption capacities of filters used in low priced counterfeit cigarettes was low and also contain hazardous chemical dibutyl phthalate. More works are needed to have a better picture.

Keywords : Chloroform, cigarette, filters, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), nicotine, smoke condensates, tobacco.

Introduction

Tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*), a member of Solanaceae family (potato and tomato belongs to the same group) is regarded to be a hazardous agricultural product¹. Tobacco contains a large number of chemicals (supposed to be about 3900 compounds), but most important biologically (physiologically, psychologically, and pharmacologically) active ingredient is addictive and toxic alkaloid nicotine which is no way fatal or carcinogenic. Processed nicotine and other flavouring agents form the ingredients for smoking.

The menace for the use of tobacco in different smoking and non smoking forms has been extensively propagated by different health organisations like WHO and other government and non government health agencies¹⁻⁶. But the smoking of cigarettes and bidis is addictive and is

used extensively till now even knowing the deleterious ill effects of tobacco smoke like shortening of life span due to diseases like chronic destructive lung diseases (COLD), ischemic heart diseases (IHD), myocardial infarction (MI), atherosclerosis, chronic bronchitis, emphysema, thrombosis, cancer in lungs, larynx and oral cavity, esophagus, bladder, kidney, pancreas etc. However, minor beneficial effects of tobacco smoking are (i) the reduction of the risk of Parkinson diseases, Alzheimer dementia and (ii) beneficial relief to some gynecological disorders.

Smoke from the burning tip of cigarettes (having a temperature range of 350-900 °C in oxygen deficient conditions) pollutes the body system and ambient air due to distribution of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons. The compounds contain C₁₃ to C₃₆ hydrocarbons with odd to even C predominance, maximum values are C₂₇-

^aPresent address : Geological Survey of India (E.R.), Salt Lake, Kolkata-700 091, India.

C_{33} with *n*-dotriacontane (C_{32} straight chain compounds)⁷. There are more high molecular weight toxic and hazardous polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. Some of the compounds are naphthalene, acenaphthalene, fluorene, phenanthrene, fluoranthrene, benz(α)pyrene (BAP-carcinogenic bio indicator), crysene, benz(*a,h*)anthracene, benzo(*g,h,i*)perylene, terpenes, phytosterols, pesticides. Other important compounds are toxic gases CO and CN, butadiene, benzene, acrolein, aromatic amines like 4-amino biphenyl, 2-naphthylamine, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, catechol, nitromethane, ethylene dioxide, acrylonitrile, ethylene carbamate, cadmium, polonium 248 (carcinogens, also affect heart, lungs, blood vessels). There are also tobacco specific nitrosoamines (carcinogens) like 4-(methylnitrosamino)-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butanone (NNK), *N*-nitrosornicotine (NNN), 4-(methylnitrosamino)-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butanol (NNAL) and its metabolite NNAL-glucuronide (measured in the urine of smokers and smokeless tobacco users). The list is enormous. However smoking is a widely used delicacy to get mental satisfaction. It is assumed to improve mental functions, enhances alertness, information processing and memory retention. Tobacco smoking, though detrimental, helps business, employment and national economy.

Efforts have therefore been made to make smoking less harmful i.e. smoking may be made health friendly. In order to reduce the harmful contents like nictines, tar and toxic hydrocarbons, aldehydes, phenols and related matters in smoke aerosols or condensates, different corrective measures have been taken by the cigarette manufacturing companies^{1,8,9}. These are (i) modification of curing and processing tobacco to reduce nitration which reduces carcinogenic nitrosamines, (ii) use of suitable blends of tobacco leaves in the cigarettes, (iii) use of perforated paper covering the cigarette to increase the supply of oxygen to make tobacco blends in the cigarettes well ventilated effectively reducing the concentrations of CO, PAH and other volatile substances in the smoke aerosol or condensate, (iv) decrease in the tobacco contents of the cigarettes, (v) introduction of filter (of different lengths) tipped cigarettes containing smoke condensate absorbent chemicals. Filters are expected to absorb considerable portions of nicotine, tar and other harmful particulate matters or fine particles formed during combustion of cigarettes and related products in smoke aerosol or condensate when smoke passes through filter column or fil-

ter bed and (iv) filters also keep the tobacco flake out of the smoker's mouth^{1,8,9}. Naturally, filters used by the different brands of cigarettes have different adsorbents for reducing the nicotine and other toxic products deleterious to health.

In the present work attempts were made to undertake a comparative study of the chemical compositions or ingredients of the filter beds and the relative efficiency of the filters in different brands of cigarette in absorbing and reducing the toxic chemicals mentioned before.

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was used for recording the chemical constituents. The results are presented in this paper.

Materials and methods :

Chemicals : Solvents like ethanol, methanol, acetone, diethylether, dimethyl sulphoxide, chloroform used was of HPLC grade from E. Merck (India).

Experimental materials were cigarettes of different brands (purchased from the local market in Kolkata or obtained as gifts). The name of the cigarettes, the countries of manufacture and other characteristic features are described in Table 1.

Table 1

Sl. no.	Name of the cigarettes and country of origin	Length of the cigarettes (cm)	Length of the filter (cm)	Weight of the filter (g)
1.	Camel (USA)	8.22	2.01	0.1461
2.	Kool (USA)	9.80	3.06	0.2105
3.	Winston (USA)	8.22	2.03	0.1489
4.	Newport (USA)	7.95	2.03	0.1561
5.	Atlanta (USA)	8.21	2.15	0.1629
6.	Charms (India)	6.86	1.04	0.0738
7.	Special (India)	6.82	1.09	0.0724
8.	Goldflake (India)	6.88	1.11	0.0793
9.	Paris (not specified, appeared to be counterfeit)	8.36	1.94	0.1370
10.	Popa (India)	8.27	2.01	0.1501
11.	Ruili River (not specified, appeared to be counterfeit)	8.35	1.93	0.1519
12.	Tiptop (Bangladesh)	8.30	1.11	0.0742
13.	Dolphin (Myanmar, appeared to be counterfeit)	8.35	1.95	0.1503

The contents of the filter beds wrapped in cellulose acetate were found to dissolve in chloroform almost totally. Other solvents like methanol, ethanol *etc.* were not as effective as chloroform as observed from the number of peaks in GC-MS.

The unused filters or filter beds were first taken in chloroform and the contents were made upto 25 mL in volumetric flasks. The filters were found to dissolve in chloroform almost totally but some of the brands contained cotton or woolen fibres like materials insoluble in chloroform. Charcoal (activated or otherwise) were not found. 2 μ L of the solution containing the chemical constituents of the filters were injected into the GC-MS for analysis.

For the determination of ingredients like nicotine, PAH *etc.* of smoke condensates absorbed or arrested by the filter when the cigarettes were puffed completely by the same smoker, used filter beds were taken in different 10 mL volumetric flasks and the contents were dissolved in chloroform and made upto the mark.

2 μ L of the solution from each set was subjected to GC-MS analysis. The contents of the compounds in blank filter beds and in used filter beds were identified from the total ion chromatograms (TIC) of GC-MS and the mass spectrum of the compounds. The compounds were also identified by proper library matching. However some of the compounds were present in very minute quantities and could not be identified properly by library matching. The experiments were repeated thrice⁷.

Instrument :

GC-MS instrument :

The identification and characterization of the explosives and hydrocarbons present as petroleum base materials were made using Perkin-Elmer-Claurus 500 model GC-MS by injecting variable volumes of the experimental solutions in corresponding solvent through Elite 5MS column of 30 meter length. Oven temperature was programmed between 70 °C (1 min) and 300 °C (10 min) with 10 °C/min increment. The injector and interface temperatures were 180 °C and 200 °C. The system was run at the rate of constant carrier gas (helium) flow 1 ml/min. MS parameters for the analysis were : EI⁺ mode, source temperature 150°, energy 70 eV, mass range scanned 30-400 amu.

Results

The major compounds constituting the filter beds were presented in Tables 2-5. Only four representative cases of different brands are given. TICs of representative brands

Table 2. Tiptop filter and some prominent compounds in chloroform extract

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	4.96	Undecane-4,7-dimethyl	184	C ₁₃ H ₂₈
2.	5.58	2,4-Dimethyldecane	170	C ₁₂ H ₂₆
3.	6.93	Menthol	156	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O
4.	8.67	<i>m</i> -Tertbutylphenol	150	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O
5.	9.18	1,2,3-Propanetriol, triacetate (Triacetin)	218	C ₉ H ₁₄ O ₆
6.	9.60	1-Tridecene	182	C ₁₃ H ₂₆
7.	9.69	Tetradecane	198	C ₁₄ H ₃₀
8.	10.46	Decane-2,3,7-trimethyl	184	C ₁₃ H ₂₈
9.	10.97	Pentadecane	212	C ₁₅ H ₃₂
10.	11.23	2,4-Ditertbutylphenol	206	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O
11.	12.09	1-Pentadecene	210	C ₁₅ H ₃₀
12.	12.17	Hexadecane	226	C ₁₆ H ₃₄
13.	12.71	Pentadecane-2,6,10-trimethyl	254	C ₁₈ H ₃₈
14.	13.32	Heptadecane	240	C ₁₇ H ₃₆
15.	14.35	1-Nonadecene	266	C ₁₉ H ₃₈
16.	14.41	Tetracosane	338	C ₂₄ H ₅₀
17.	14.81	Neophytadiene	278	C ₂₀ H ₃₆

Table 3. Charms filter and some prominent compounds in chloroform extract

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	6.90	Menthol	156	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O
2.	8.67	<i>m</i> -Tertbutylphenol	150	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O
3.	9.12	Triacetin	218	C ₉ H ₁₄ O ₆
4.	12.09	Propanoic acid, 2-methyl-1-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl-1,3-propanediylester	286	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₄
5.	14.80	Neophytadiene	278	C ₂₀ H ₃₆
6.	15.22	Dibutylphthalate	278	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄
7.	16.27	Palmitic acid	256	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂
8.	17.99	Oleic acid	282	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂
9.	18.84	Tributylacetyl citrate (Citroflex)	402	C ₂₀ H ₃₄ O ₈
10.	20.04	Diocyladipate	370	C ₂₂ H ₄₂ O ₄

Table 4. Kool filter and some prominent compounds in chloroform extract

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	6.86	Menthol	156	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O
2.	8.52	Diacetin	176	C ₇ H ₁₂ O ₅
3.	8.67	<i>m</i> -Tertbutylphenol	150	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O
4.	9.28	Triacetin	218	C ₉ H ₁₄ O ₆
5.	9.54	1-Tetradecene	210	C ₁₅ H ₃₀
6.	9.61	Propanoic acid, 2-methyl-3-hydroxy-2,4,4-trimethyl pentylester	216	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₃
7.	11.29	2,4-Ditertbutylphenol	206	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O
8.	12.13	1-Heptadecene	238	C ₁₇ H ₃₄
9.	14.09	Benzoic acid, 1-Methylethylester	164	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂
10.	14.47	1-Nonadecene	266	C ₁₉ H ₃₈
11.	14.96	Neophytadiene	278	C ₂₀ H ₃₆
12.	21.50	1-Hentetracontanol	592	C ₄₁ H ₈₄ O
13.	22.69	Dipropylene glycol dibenzoate	342	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₅

Table 5. Dolphin (appeared to be counterfeit) filter and some prominent compounds in chloroform extract

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	9.38	Dodecane-2,6,10-trimethyl	212	C ₁₅ H ₃₂
2.	9.63	1-Tridecene	196	C ₁₄ H ₂₈
3.	9.71	Tetradecane	198	C ₁₄ H ₃₀
4.	10.46	Decane-2,3,7-trimethyl	184	C ₁₃ H ₂₈
5.	10.98	Pentadecane	212	C ₁₅ H ₃₂
6.	11.25	2,4-Ditertbutylphenol	206	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O
7.	11.61	Tetradecane-5-methyl	212	C ₁₅ H ₃₂
8.	11.68	Cyclohexane, Eicosyl-	364	C ₂₆ H ₅₂
9.	11.84	Pentadecane, 2-methyl	226	C ₁₆ H ₃₄
10.	12.10	1-Pentadecene	210	C ₁₅ H ₃₀
11.	12.18	Hexadecane	226	C ₁₆ H ₃₄
12.	12.71	Pentadecane-2,6,10-trimethyl	254	C ₁₈ H ₃₈
13.	13.33	Heptadecane	240	C ₁₇ H ₃₆
14.	13.35	Squalane	422	C ₃₀ H ₆₂
15.	14.36	1-Nonadecene	266	C ₁₉ H ₃₈
16.	14.43	Octadecane	254	C ₁₈ H ₃₈
17.	14.49	Phytane	282	C ₂₀ H ₄₂
18.	14.82	Neophytadiene	278	C ₂₀ H ₃₆
19.	15.22	Dibutylphthalate	278	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄
20.	15.56	Heneicosane	296	C ₂₁ H ₄₄
21.	21.28	Diisooctylphthalate	390	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄

Table 6

Sl. no.	Filter bed composition	Examples
1.	Triacetin based	Tiptop (Bangladesh), Popa (India)
2.	Triacetin + Citroflex based	Charms, Special, Goldflake etc. (India)
3.	Triacetin + Glycol dibenzoate based	Kool, Newport, Camel etc. (USA)
4.	Without triacetin, but with phthate compounds (not dissolved in chloroform)	Dolphin, Paris, Ruili River (all appeared to be counterfeit)

and MS spectrum of some of the compounds were presented in Figs. 1–6. Most of the brands had similarities in their chemical constituents in cigarettes with minor variations or variations in the concentrations of the constituents. Similarly the used filter beds containing the constituents of cigarette smoke condensates were also presented in Tables 7–10. Only four representative cases of different brands are given. TICs of some consumed filter beds of representative brands were presented in Figs. 7–9. The TIC of triacetin and nicotine in a consumed filter and the mass spectrum of nicotine were presented in Figs. 10 and 11. The results were only qualitative⁸.

Discussion

The purpose of the present study is to find the efficiency of the filters in removing nicotine, PAHs, nitrosamines etc. from cigarette smoke aerosols passing through the filters before entering the body systems. However, the results are difficult to interpret as a large number of extraneous factors are involved with different brands of cigarettes. There are usually three different types of tobacco used for the preparation of cigarettes¹.

(i) Flue cured Virginia (FCV) tobacco (aromatic and colourful processed tobacco).

(ii) Natu tobacco : aromatic type sun cured tobacco, generally used to make cheaper brands of cigarettes.

(iii) Burley tobacco : light air cured tobacco.

Probably flue cured virginia tobacco was used in all the brands of cigarettes examined. There are also differences in composition of different types depending on the places of origin and their biosynthetic pathways of pro-

Fig. 1. TIC of chloroform extracts of Dolphin filter.

Fig. 2. TIC of chloroform extracts of Kool filter.

Fig. 3. TIC of chloroform extracts of Charms filter.

Fig. 4. Mass spectrum of triacetin obtained from a cigarette filter.

Fig. 5. Mass spectrum of citroflex obtained from a cigarette filter.

Fig. 6. Mass spectrum of dipropylene glycol dibenzoate obtained from a cigarette filter.

Table 7. Some prominent compounds found in consumed Tiptop filter (mainly triacetin base)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	4.25	2,4-Dimethylfuran	96	C ₈ H ₈ O
2.	4.48	Pyrimidine-5-methyl	94	C ₅ H ₆ N ₂
3.	4.51	2-Vinylfuran	94	C ₆ H ₆ O
4.	4.72	DL-Limonene	136	C ₁₀ H ₁₆
5.	5.02	2,3-Dimethyl-2-Cyclopenten-1-one	110	C ₇ H ₁₀ O
6.	5.26	2-Cyclopenten-1-one-2,3,4-trimethyl	124	C ₈ H ₁₂ O
7.	5.48	Benzyl alcohol	108	C ₇ H ₈ O
8.	5.84	<i>p</i> -Cresol	108	C ₇ H ₈ O
9.	6.47	Naphthalene-1,2-dihydro	130	C ₁₀ H ₁₀
10.	6.80	2,5-Xylenol	122	C ₈ H ₁₀ O
11.	7.11	Naphthalene	128	C ₁₀ H ₈
12.	8.55	1-Indanone	132	C ₉ H ₈ O
13.	9.29	Nicotine	162	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂
14.	10.14	1 <i>H</i> -Indole-6-methyl	131	C ₉ H ₉ N
15.	12.41	9 <i>H</i> -Fluorene	166	C ₁₃ H ₁₀
16.	12.79	Diphenylamine	169	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N
17.	13.57	14-Heptadecenal	252	C ₁₇ H ₃₂ O
18.	13.63	Dihydrophytol	298	C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O
19.	15.67	Farnesyl acetone A	262	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O
20.	24.02	Nonacosane	408	C ₂₉ H ₆₀
21.	24.59	Heptacosane	380	C ₂₇ H ₅₆
22.	24.78	Pentatriacontane	492	C ₃₅ H ₇₂
23.	25.15	Stigmasta-5,22-dien-3-ol-acetate(3.β.22z)-	454	C ₃₁ H ₅₀ O ₂
24.	25.36	Hexatriacontane	506	C ₃₆ H ₇₄
25.	25.70	Tetracontane	618	C ₄₄ H ₉₀
26.	26.17	Vitamin E	430	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₂
27.	26.45	Tritetracontane	604	C ₄₃ H ₈₈

Table 8. Some prominent compounds found in consumed Charms filter (triacetin and citroflex base)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	4.40	Phenol	94	C ₆ H ₆ O
2.	4.69	DL-Limonene	136	C ₁₀ H ₁₆
3.	4.86	Cyclohexane-1-methyl-4-methylene	110	C ₈ H ₁₄
4.	4.96	Beta-thujone	152	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O
5.	5.36	<i>o</i> -Cresol	108	C ₇ H ₈ O
6.	5.45	Acetophenone	120	C ₈ H ₈ O
7.	5.76	2-Methoxyphenol	124	C ₈ H ₁₀ O

Table-8 (contd.)

8.	6.17	2-Cyclopenten-1-one-3-ethyl-2-hydroxy	126	C ₇ H ₁₀ O ₂
9.	6.75	2,4-Xylenol	122	C ₈ H ₁₀ O
10.	7.05	Naphthalene	128	C ₁₀ H ₈
11.	8.30	Phenol-4-ethyl-2-methoxy	152	C ₉ H ₁₂ O ₂
12.	8.49	1-Indanone	132	C ₉ H ₈ O
13.	8.83	1 <i>H</i> -Indole	117	C ₈ H ₇ N
14.	9.55	Nicotine	162	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂
15.	12.35	9 <i>H</i> -Fluorene	166	C ₁₃ H ₁₀
16.	12.70	Megastigmatrienone	190	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O
17.	13.22	1-Octadecene	252	C ₁₈ H ₃₆
18.	13.60	Dihydrophytol	298	C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O
19.	15.25	3-Eicosyne	278	C ₂₀ H ₃₈
20.	15.44	Hexadecane	226	C ₁₆ H ₃₄
21.	15.64	Farnesol	222	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O
22.	22.49	Pentacosane	352	C ₂₅ H ₅₂
23.	23.37	Squalene	410	C ₃₀ H ₅₀
24.	24.02	Nonacosane	408	C ₂₉ H ₆₀
25.	24.58	Tetatriacontane	478	C ₃₄ H ₇₀
26.	25.36	Hexatriacontane	506	C ₃₆ H ₇₄
27.	25.72	Tetracontane	562	C ₄₀ H ₈₂
28.	26.15	Vitamin E	430	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₂
29.	26.48	Tetratetracontane	618	C ₄₄ H ₉₀

Table 9. Some prominent compounds found in consumed Kool filter (triacetin and dipropylenglycoldibenzoate base)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	4.25	2-Cyclopenten-1-one-3-methyl	96	C ₈ H ₈ O
2.	4.54	Phenol	94	C ₆ H ₆ O
3.	4.71	DL-Limonene	136	C ₁₀ H ₁₆
4.	4.95	3,4-Dimethyl-cyclohexanol	128	C ₈ H ₁₆ O
5.	5.03	2,3-Dimethyl-2-cyclopenten-1-one	110	C ₇ H ₁₀ O
6.	5.28	2-Cyclopenten-1-one-3,4,5-trimethyl	124	C ₈ H ₁₂ O
7.	5.47	<i>o</i> -Cresol	108	C ₇ H ₈ O
8.	5.87	<i>p</i> -Cresol	108	C ₇ H ₈ O
9.	7.06	Naphthalene	128	C ₁₀ H ₈
10.	8.55	1 <i>H</i> -Inden-1-one-2,3-dihydro	132	C ₉ H ₈ O
11.	8.83	Methylnaphthalene	142	C ₁₁ H ₁₀
12.	8.93	4-Hydroxy-3-methyl acetophenone	150	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂

Table-9 (contd.)

13.	9.20	Nicotine	162	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂
14.	10.10	1 <i>H</i> -Indole-6-methyl	131	C ₉ H ₉ N
15.	10.49	Farnesol	222	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O
16.	12.39	9 <i>H</i> -Fluorene	166	C ₁₃ H ₁₀
17.	12.75	Megastigmatrienone	190	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O
18.	13.24	1-Octadecene	252	C ₁₈ H ₃₆
19.	13.32	Hexadecane	226	C ₁₆ H ₃₄
20.	13.57	Hexadecanal	240	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O
21.	13.62	Dihydrophytol	298	C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O
22.	14.35	1-Nonadecene	266	C ₁₉ H ₃₈
23.	15.56	Squalene	410	C ₃₀ H ₅₀
24.	15.62	Caryophyllene	204	C ₁₅ H ₂₄
25.	16.41	1-Octadecanol	270	C ₁₈ H ₃₈ O
26.	22.49	Pentacosane	352	C ₂₅ H ₅₂
27.	23.26	Hexacosane	366	C ₂₆ H ₅₄
28.	24.02	Triacontane	422	C ₃₀ H ₆₂
29.	24.57	Tetratriacontane	478	C ₃₄ H ₇₀
30.	24.79	Hexatriacontane	506	C ₃₆ H ₇₄
31.	25.34	Tetracontane	562	C ₄₀ H ₈₂
32.	25.70	Tetratetracontane	618	C ₄₄ H ₉₀
33.	26.15	Vitamin E	430	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₂

Table 10. Some prominent compounds found in consumed Dolphin (appeared to be counterfeit) filter (phthalate compound base)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	4.73	DL-Limonene	136	C ₁₀ H ₁₆
2.	4.45	2-Cyclopenten-1-one-3-methyl	96	C ₈ H ₈ O
3.	4.97	Undecane-5,7-dimethyl	184	C ₁₃ H ₂₈
4.	5.01	Aminopyrazine	95	C ₄ H ₅ N ₃
5.	5.11	2,3-Dimethyl-2-cyclopenten-1-one	110	C ₇ H ₁₀ O
6.	5.99	<i>p</i> -Cresol	108	C ₇ H ₈ O
7.	6.89	1-Tetradecanol	214	C ₁₄ H ₃₀ O
8.	8.39	Tetradecane	198	C ₁₄ H ₃₀
9.	8.67	Methylnaphthalene	142	C ₁₁ H ₁₀
10.	9.26	Nicotin	162	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂
11.	13.59	Hexadecanal	240	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O
12.	13.66	Dihydrophytol	298	C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O
13.	22.53	Heptacosane	380	C ₂₇ H ₅₆
14.	23.35	Pentatriacontane	492	C ₃₅ H ₇₂
15.	23.47	Squalene	410	C ₃₀ H ₅₀
16.	24.13	Nonacosane	408	C ₂₉ H ₆₀
17.	25.50	Hexatriacontane	506	C ₃₆ H ₇₄
18.	25.87	Tritetracontane	604	C ₄₃ H ₈₈
19.	26.34	Vitamin E	430	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₂

duction of tobacco. It is apparent that tobacco undergoes substantial changes during growing, curing, processing and storing.

During preparation of cigarettes, tobacco leaves, stems and other ingredients are blended to achieve specific nicotine content, pH, taste, flavour and aroma. Alkaline pH make nicotine bioavailable. Nitrate contents or nitration during processing tobacco increase harmful nitrosoamines. Naturally, there should be wide variation in the composition of tobacco and other ingredients in different brands of cigarettes. The composition of the smoke condensates or aerosols must be different for different brands.

However, the most important limitation of finding out the efficiency of filters was the absence of data of smoke condensates from the complete combustion of same brand of cigarettes with filter tip and without filter tip. Moreover, no work could be done to determine the compositions of the smoke condensates from different brands of cigarettes and estimate at least the important constituents like nicotine or other PAHs in smoke aerosols and the constituents absorbed or arrested by plasticizers or absorbers in the filter beds. Other limitations were

(i) There were differences in the compositions of nicotiana tabacum and other compounds in different brand of cigarettes.

(ii) Only chloroform extract was taken for investigation.

(iii) Length and nature of the GC column might have been inadequate to identify more compounds.

In order to throw light on the efficiency of the filters as explained earlier, it is necessary to have an idea about the compositions of different filters. It was possible for us to collect thirteen brands of cigarettes. The name of the cigarette brands, their country of origin, length of the cigarettes, length of the filter beds, effective length of the cigarettes are given in Table 1. The representative compounds present in Tiptop cigarettes and other Indian and foreign cigarettes are given in Tables 2-5. Based on the compositions of the filter beds, the filters may be classified into four categories (Table 6).

Many of the compounds are hazardous only when they interact with the biological systems and are formed due

Fig. 7. TIC of chloroform extracts of consumed Dolphin filter.

Fig. 8. TIC of chloroform extracts of consumed Kool filter.

Fig. 9. TIC of chloroform extracts of consumed Charms filter.

Fig. 10. Nicotine and triacetin in consumed Charms filter.

Fig. 11. Mass spectrum of nicotine obtained from a consumed filter.

to biological interactions. Mostly the hazardous compounds listed are formed due to biological interactions. The quantitative amounts of the compounds are hardly available from the smoke condensate records. Moreover, biological effects of these compounds and proper correlation of the exposure of the compounds with cancer, heart attacks could not be made. Removal of nicotine can be regarded to be most important as nicotine is converted to be hazardous metabolite cotinine (a measure of nicotine exposure), cotinine-*N*-oxide, cotinine glucuronide, nicotine-*N*-oxide and nicotine glucuronide and particularly *N*-nitrosamines like NNN, NNK etc. Nitrosamines require special methods for extraction and nitrosamines were not expected in CHCl_3 extracts. Properly cured and processed cigarettes may have low concentrations of nitrosoamines. Concentration of *N*-nitrosamines in tobacco smoke condensate is very small. Nitrosamines can be obtained as metabolite by interaction with saliva and liver in body systems. Filters can reduce the hazardous substances to a certain extent but cannot eliminate many of the hazardous chemicals associated with smoke condensate. A critical analysis of the efficiency of different cigarettes are difficult as besides other factors : (i) lengths of the filters (ii)

tobacco contents of the cigarettes were different. However, in order to have some idea about the nicotine removal capacity of the filters, areas of nicotine (considering mass 162) using SIM mode were measured. The results are presented in Table 11. Similarly areas of triacetin (considering the main peak of mass 145) in the filters were measured using SIM mode. The results are presented in Table 12. Absolute concentrations of nicotine and triacetin could not be determined due to non availability of appropriate standards. The greater area of nicotine indicated greater nicotine removal capacity. A rough parallelism however existed between greater triacetin content with greater removal of nicotine. But there were other ingredients besides triacetin. Attempts have been made to determine the areas of nicotine per g of filter materials. The results (Table 11) show that filters of Goldflake, Winston, Newport and Camel are more efficient in removing nicotine compared to those of Tiptop, Paris, Dolphin (so named). It is to be noted that different low cost king size cigarettes like Dolphin, Paris, Ruili River purchased from local 11 markets were probably counterfeit cigarettes and not from company origin. The packets did not include packing date, batch number, country of

Table 11. Nicotine area counts as obtained from different cigarette filters

Sl. no.	Name of the cigarettes	Retention time (min)	Nicotine area count (in arbitrary units)	Nicotine area count per g of filter material (in arbitrary units)
1.	Charms (India)	6.87	92850	1258130
2.	Goldflake (India)	6.59	146103	1842408
3.	Special (India)	6.69	100892	1393535
4.	Newport (USA)	6.42	237157	1519263
5.	Camel (USA)	6.37	219149	1499993
6.	Winston (USA)	6.40	258219	1734177
7.	Tiptop (Bangladesh)	6.82	58294	785633
8.	Dolphin (appeared to be counterfeit)	6.74	106718	710033
9.	Paris (appeared to be counterfeit)	6.62	142030	1036715

Table 12. Triacetin area counts as obtained from different cigarette filters

Sl. no.	Name of the cigarettes	Retention time (min)	Triacetin area count (in arbitrary units)
1.	Charms (India)	6.14	506136
2.	Goldflake (India)	6.15	361619
3.	Special (India)	6.10	498937
4.	Newport (USA)	6.06	776025
5.	Camel (USA)	6.03	774043
6.	Winston (USA)	6.05	703763
7.	Tiptop (Bangladesh)	6.09	511527

origin, health warning and other manufacturing details. These cigarettes probably used smuggled tobacco from the companies (quality of tobacco was good and almost similar in most cases) but used low cost indigenous filter made up of cotton or other fibers insoluble in chloroform but were not identified. Instead of triacetin, dibutylphthalate (suspected tetraoxygen, endocrine disruptor and a banned product)¹⁰ and diisooctylphthalate were used as plasticizer with higher hydrocarbons and squalene, a biomarker.

Phthalate exposures adversely affects respiratory troubles in children¹¹ but nothing has been reported against iso-octylphthalate. Almost all the top class cigarette companies in the world use triacetin (glycerine triacetate) as a plasticizer and humectant in filters. Charms, Special, Goldflake use triacetin, citroflex (tributylacetyl citrate as plasticizer, humectant and fragrance carrier) and iso-octylphthalate. Triacetin and dipropylene glycolbenzoate were present in Kool, Camel and Newport cigarettes but the last one also contains diethylene glycol dibenzoate as plas-

ticizer. These compounds are obtained in top class cigarettes (Newport, Camel etc.) but Atlanta contains diacetin, triacetin and dibutylphthalate. Menthol was used in many filters. It is a local anaesthetic, having cooling effect and relieves throat irritation. It is used in Kool, Tiptop, Charms etc. but not in the filters of Newport, Dolphin, Camel etc. Neophytadiene was used as an additive in many cigarettes (Tiptop, Charms, Dolphin etc.) to improve aroma and evaporation rates.

However, a large number of other compounds including high molecular hydrocarbons were also present in the filters as will be evident from the list of other prominent chemicals in different filters (Tables 2-5).

The effectiveness of the filters can be assessed from the removal of different hazardous chemicals like hydrocarbons including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, aldehydes, ketones, CO, HCN amines etc. but important being nicotine and nicotine related compounds present in smoke condensates. Naturally, the substances were expected to be present in used filters.

The representative tables showed the removal or reduction of compounds present in tobacco smoke condensates from different cigarettes, the compositions of which were found to be slightly different. However, the results suffered as the contents of tobacco in different cigarettes were different. But to have a better idea, areas of nicotine contents in total tobacco in CHCl₃ in some selected cigarettes had been made and compared with nicotine contents (in terms of area count) in the used filters of the corresponding cigarettes.

The results indicated the relative efficiency of the filters

in removing nicotine were different. However, in all cases the reduction of nicotine from the smoke condensates were small. Preliminary experiments presented here must be supplemented carefully with further experiments.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. C. N. Bhattacharya, Director, Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata for all possible help and encouragement. Authors are also thankful to Mr. Sushovon Lahiri for gift samples of USA based cigarettes and officers and staffs of Explosive Division, CFSL, Kolkata. One of us (AC) expresses his deep sense of gratitude to his wife Mrs. Sonali Chakraborty, for inspiration and mental support.

References

1. V. M. Sivaramakrishnan, "Tobacco and Areca nut", Orient Langmans, Chennai, 2001.
2. A. Jemal, M. J. Thun, Lynn A. G. Ries, H. L. Howe, H. K. Weir, M. M. Center, E. Ward, Xiao-Cheng Wu, C. Ehemann, R. Anderson, U. A. Ajani, B. Kohler and B. K. Edwards, *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.*, 2008, **100**, 1672.
3. Heart disease and Stroke Statistics-2011 Update, A Report from the American Heart Association, *Circulation*, 2011, **123**, e18-e209.
4. Report on Oral Tobacco use and its implications in South East India, WHO SEARO 2004, Chapter 1, Oral Tobacco Products, pp. 6-20.
5. The Scientific Basis of Tobacco Product Regulation, WHO Technical Report Series 945, 2007, Chapter 1-5, pp. 1-96.
6. Smokeless Tobacco and some Tobacco specific *N*-nitrosamines, IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Human, Vol. 89, Lyon, France, 2007.
7. M. F. Fadzil and N. M. Tahir, *The Malaysian Journal of Analytical Sciences*, 2007, **2**, 8.
8. C. E. Johnson, "Development of cigarette components to meet Industry needs", Paper presented at the 52nd Tobacco Science Research Conference, September 14-16, 1998, Atlanta, GA.
9. Cigarette Filters from wikipedia.
10. Council Directive of 27 July 1976 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to cosmetic products (76/768/EEC), The Council of the European Communities.
11. J. A. Hoppin, R. Ulmer and S. J. London, Phthalate exposure and pulmonary function. *Environ Health Perspect*, 112:571-574, <http://dx.doi./10.1289/ehp.6564>.

